

A FUZZY APPROACH TO OPTIMAL EQUIPMENT REPLACEMENT USING TRIANGULAR FUZZY NUMBERS

Archana Dubey^{1*} and Dr. Rekha Jain²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics,
Medicaps University, Indore MP, India.

²Professor, Department of Mathematics, Medicaps University, Indore MP, India.
Email: ¹dubeyarchana28@gmail.com, ²rjain5129@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16531524

Abstract

The study focuses on resolving the issue of when to replace equipment in situations where future conditions and costs are uncertain. To capture the imprecision often present in such real-life scenarios, the model incorporates fuzzy set theory. Triangular fuzzy numbers are used to express the uncertain cost components. The approach aims to determine the most appropriate point in time for equipment replacement under fuzzy conditions. Its practical relevance is supported by a real-life example that demonstrates how the method works in application.

1. INTRODUCTION

In practical applications, equipment replacement plays a vital role in economic decision-making. In engineering economics, replacement analysis theory is used to determine optimal strategies for maintenance and replacement decisions.

When a production facility is new, its machines operate at full efficiency. Over time and with usage, this efficiency gradually decreases as the equipment ages. To restore efficiency, maintenance is required. After the first maintenance, performance declines slightly, and with each subsequent maintenance, the performance decreases further. This deterioration continues until the machine's efficiency drops to an undesirable level. At this point, it becomes uneconomical to maintain the facility due to the high maintenance costs and increased production costs per unit. Therefore, replacement of the facility becomes necessary.

In real-world situations marked by uncertainty, decision-makers frequently rely on Zadeh's [1] fuzzy set theory as a more suitable framework for determining the optimal equipment replacement time within an acceptable range, rather than pinpointing an exact value. Several researchers, including Bellman [2], Dreyfus [3], Mahdavi and Mahdavi M. [4], and Zhao et al. [5], have investigated various replacement models under traditional (non-fuzzy) conditions.

Later, Chang [6] categorized strategic replacement in fuzzy terms. Balaganesan and Ganesan [7, 8] investigated the economic life of equipment using fuzzy and intuitionistic fuzzy approaches, considering changes in monetary value. Al-Najjar and Alsayouf [9] explored a fuzzy approach in maintenance decision-making models involving multiple criteria.

Biswas and Pramanik [10, 11], along with El-Kholy and Abdelalim [12], employed fuzzy ranking methods to assess the economic life of equipment, both in scenarios where the monetary value remains constant and when it changes. Esogbue and Hearnnes [13] explored replacement models using a fuzzy set theoretic framework. Generally, these authors have discussed fuzzy replacement models by translating them into equivalent classical models. However, this paper determines the replacement time of equipment under fuzzy conditions without converting it into a classical version.

The remainder of our study is structured as follows: Section 2 covers the fundamentals of fuzzy sets, including basic concepts and arithmetic operations of triangular fuzzy numbers. Section 3 outlines the algorithm for our proposed model. Section 4 presents a real-life example illustrating the replacement model. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusion of our findings.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Lotfi A. Zadeh introduced the concept of fuzzy sets in 1965 as a mathematical framework designed to represent uncertainty and imprecision in data.

2.1 Definition

A fuzzy set \tilde{A} defined on the set of real numbers R is said to be a fuzzy number, if its membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}: R \rightarrow [0,1]$ has the following characteristics:

- (i) \tilde{A} is convex i.e. $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(\lambda x_1 + (1 - \lambda)x_2) \geq \min\{\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x_1), \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x_2)\}, \lambda \in [0,1],$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in R$
- (ii) \tilde{A} is normal i.e. there exist an $x \in R$ such that $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = 1$
- (iii) $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)$ is upper semi continuous on R
- (iv) The $supp(\tilde{A})$ is bounded and closed.

2.2 Definition

A fuzzy number \tilde{A} on R is a triangular fuzzy number if its membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}: R \rightarrow [0,1]$ has the following characteristics:

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a_1}{a_2-a_1}, & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \frac{a_3-x}{a_3-a_2}, & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

We denote this triangular fuzzy number as $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$. We use $F(R)$ to denote the set of all triangular fuzzy numbers defined on R .

2.3 Definition

Parametric type Triangular Fuzzy Number

A triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3) \in F(R)$ can also be represented as a pair $\tilde{A} = (\underline{a}, \bar{a})$ of function $\underline{a}(p), \bar{a}(p)$, for $0 \leq p \leq 1$ which satisfies the following requirement:

- (i) $\underline{a}(p)$ is a bounded monotonic increasing left continuous function.
- (ii) $\bar{a}(p)$ is a bounded monotonic decreasing left continuous function
- (iii) $\underline{a}(p) \leq \bar{a}(p), 0 \leq p \leq 1$

then the parametric form of the TFN is defined as $\tilde{A} = (a_0, a_*, a^*)$ where $a_* = (a_0 - \underline{a})$,

$a^* = (\bar{a} - a_0)$ are called the left fuzziness index function and the right fuzziness index function respectively and $\underline{a}(p) = a_1 + (a_2 - a_1)p, \bar{a}(p) = a_3 - (a_3 - a_2)p$.

For an arbitrary triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (\underline{a}, \bar{a})$ the number $a_0 = \frac{a(1) + \bar{a}(1)}{2}$ i.e $a_0 = a_2$ is said to be location index number of \tilde{A}

2.4 Arithmetic Operations on Triangular Fuzzy Numbers

Ming Ma et al. [15] have proposed a new fuzzy arithmetic operation based upon both location index and fuzziness index functions. The location index number is taken in the ordinary arithmetic, whereas the fuzziness index functions are considered to follow the lattice rule which is least upper bound in the lattice L. That is for, $a, b \in L$ we define $a \vee b = \max \{a, b\}$ and $a \wedge b = \min \{a, b\}$.

For any two triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_0, a_*, a^*), \tilde{B} = (b_0, b_*, b^*)$ the arithmetic operations on the fuzzy numbers are defined by $\tilde{a} * \tilde{b} = (a_0 * b_0, a_* \vee b_*, a^* \vee b^*)$. In particular for any two triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_0, a_*, a^*), \tilde{B} = (b_0, b_*, b^*)$ we define:

- (i) Addition: $\tilde{A} + \tilde{B} = (a_0, a_*, a^*) + (b_0, b_*, b^*) = (a_0 + b_0, \max\{a_*, b_*\}, \max\{a^*, b^*\})$
- (ii) Subtraction: $\tilde{A} - \tilde{B} = (a_0, a_*, a^*) - (b_0, b_*, b^*) = (a_0 - b_0, \max\{a_*, b_*\}, \max\{a^*, b^*\})$
- (iii) Multiplication: $\tilde{A} \times \tilde{B} = (a_0, a_*, a^*) \times (b_0, b_*, b^*) = (a_0 \times b_0, \max\{a_*, b_*\}, \max\{a^*, b^*\})$
- (iv) Division: $\tilde{A} \div \tilde{B} = (a_0, a_*, a^*) \div (b_0, b_*, b^*) = (a_0 \div b_0, \max\{a_*, b_*\}, \max\{a^*, b^*\})$

3. PROPOSED MODEL: TRIANGULAR FUZZY REPLACEMENT MODEL

The primary objective of this paper is to determine the optimal replacement time (in discrete time intervals) for an item whose **maintenance (or running) cost increases over time**, under the assumption that the **value of money remains constant** throughout the analysis period.

Let:

\tilde{C} : Fuzzy capital cost of the item

$\tilde{S}(t)$: Fuzzy scrap value of the item at t time units

$\tilde{f}(t)$: Fuzzy running or maintenance cost over t time units (e.g., hours, months, years)

N: Optimum period (in hours, months, years) when the machine must be replaced

\tilde{T} : Total Cost at time t = C- S(t)+ f(t)

Since the total maintenance cost incurred on the item during N (hours, months, years)

$$= \sum_{t=1}^N f(t)$$

The total cost incurred on the item during N (hours, months, years)

$$\tilde{T}(N) = \tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t) + \sum_{t=1}^N f(t)$$

∴ Average total cost incurred on the item during 'N' years is $\tilde{Z}(N) = \frac{\tilde{T}(N)}{N} = \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N} + \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N}$

$\tilde{Z}(N)$ is minimum if $\tilde{Z}(N + 1) \geq \tilde{Z}(N) \leq \tilde{Z}(N - 1)$ is satisfied

Or we say $\tilde{Z}(N)$ is minimum if $\tilde{Z}(N + 1) - \tilde{Z}(N) \geq 0$ and $\tilde{Z}(N) - \tilde{Z}(N - 1) \geq 0$

Now

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{Z}(N+1) - \tilde{Z}(N) &= \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N+1} f(t)}{N+1} + \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N+1} \right] - \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N} + \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N+1} f(t)}{N+1} - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N} \right] + \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N+1} - \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N+1} + \frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N} \right] + \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N+1} - \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} + \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N+1} - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N} \right] + \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N+1} - \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} + \sum_{t=1}^N f(t) \left[\frac{1}{N+1} - \frac{1}{N} \right] \right] + \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N+1} - \frac{\tilde{C} - \tilde{S}(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} + \sum_{t=1}^N f(t) \left[-\frac{1}{N(N+1)} \right] \right] + \left[\frac{-(\tilde{C} - S(t))}{N(N+1)} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} - \frac{\left[\sum_{t=1}^N f(t) \right]}{N(N+1)} \right] - \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - S(t)}{N(N+1)} \right] \\
 &= \frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} - \frac{\left[\sum_{t=1}^N f(t) \right]}{N(N+1)} - \frac{1}{(N+1)} \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - S(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} - \frac{1}{(N+1)} \left[\frac{\tilde{C} - S(t) + \sum_{t=1}^N f(t)}{N} \right] \\
 &= \frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} - \frac{1}{(N+1)} [\tilde{Z}(N)]
 \end{aligned}$$

$\tilde{Z}(N)$ is minimum for which $\tilde{Z}(N+1) - \tilde{Z}(N) \geq 0$,

$$\Rightarrow \frac{f(N+1)}{N+1} - \frac{1}{(N+1)} [\tilde{Z}(N)] \geq 0$$

$$\Rightarrow f(N+1) \geq \tilde{Z}(N)$$

Similarly $\tilde{Z}(N) \leq \tilde{Z}(N-1)$

$$\Rightarrow f(N) \leq \tilde{Z}(N-1)$$

is used to determine the optimum replacement period.

Therefore, the replacement policy is as follows:

- (i) *If the maintenance cost expected in the next year ($n + 1$) is less than or equal to the average total cost per year up to now (year n), then it is still economical to keep the equipment, and replacement is not advisable.*
- (ii) *If the maintenance cost expected in the next year ($n+1$) is greater than the average total cost per year calculated up to the current year (n), then it is no longer economical to retain the equipment, and it should be replaced.*

4. EXAMPLE

4.1 Example

A truck owner purchased three identical trucks, each with a fuzzy cost given by (8300000, 8350000, 8400000) rupees. According to past records, the expected resale value of each truck is (204000, 206000, 208000) rupees. The fuzzy maintenance cost incurred per 100 hours of operation (with 100 hours = 1 unit and Rs.10,000 = 1 cost unit) is shown in Table 1. Determine the most cost-effective time to replace the trucks with new one.

Table 1: Maintenance fuzzy cost per 100 hours

(Here we take 100 hours = 1unit and Rs 10000 =1 unit.)

Time(N)	Maintenance fuzzy cost $\tilde{f}(t)$ of trucks
1	$\langle 12, 13, 13.5 \rangle$
2	$\langle 24, 24.5, 25 \rangle$
3	$\langle 29, 30.5, 31 \rangle$
4	$\langle 36.5, 37.5, 38 \rangle$
5	$\langle 44, 45.5, 47 \rangle$
6	$\langle 59, 60.5, 62 \rangle$
7	$\langle 89, 91.5, 94 \rangle$
8	$\langle 109, 124, 139 \rangle$
9	$\langle 169, 184, 194 \rangle$
10	$\langle 219, 229, 236.5 \rangle$

Solution: To solve this problem, we take 100 hours=1unit and Rs.10000=1 unit.

We first transform the fuzzy maintenance cost into its parametric form (see Table 2)

Table 2: Maintenance fuzzy cost and its parametric form

Time(N)	$\tilde{f}(t)$	Parametric form of $\tilde{f}(t)$
1	$\langle 12, 13, 13.5 \rangle$	$\langle 13, 1-1p, 0.5-0.5p \rangle$
2	$\langle 24, 24.5, 25 \rangle$	$\langle 24.5, 0.5-0.5p, 0.5-0.5p \rangle$
3	$\langle 29, 30.5, 31 \rangle$	$\langle 30.5, 1.5p-1.5p, 0.5-0.5p \rangle$
4	$\langle 36.5, 37.5, 38 \rangle$	$\langle 37.5, 1-1p, 0.5-0.5p \rangle$
5	$\langle 44, 45.5, 47 \rangle$	$\langle 45.5, 1.5p-1.5p, 1.5p-1.5p \rangle$
6	$\langle 59, 60.5, 62 \rangle$	$\langle 60.5, 1.5p-1.5p, 1.5p-1.5p \rangle$
7	$\langle 89, 91.5, 94 \rangle$	$\langle 91.5, 2.5p-2.5p, 2.5p-2.5p \rangle$
8	$\langle 109, 124, 139 \rangle$	$\langle 124, 15-15p, 15-15p \rangle$
9	$\langle 169, 184, 194 \rangle$	$\langle 184, 15-15p, 10-10p \rangle$
10	$\langle 219, 229, 236.5 \rangle$	$\langle 229, 10-10p, 7.5-7.5p \rangle$

The average total cost per hundred hours is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Determination of Fuzzy Optimal Replacement Time

(All monetary values are in units where Rs. 10000 = 1 unit and time is per 100 hours)

Time (N)	f(t) (Fuzzy Running Cost)	S̃(t) (Scrap Value)	$\sum \tilde{f}(t)$	$\bar{T} = \bar{C} - \bar{S}(t) + \sum_{t=1}^N f(t)$	Z(N)	R(Z(N))
1	{13,1-1p, 0.5-0.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{13,1-1p, 0.5-0.5p}	{827.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{827.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	827.4
2	{24.5, 0.5-0.5p, 0.5-0.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{37.5, 1-p, 0.5-0.5p}	{851.9, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{425.95, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	425.95
3	{30.5, 1.5p-1.5p, 0.5-0.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{68, 1.5-1.5p, 0.5-0.5p}	{882.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{294.13, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	294.13
4	{37.5, 1-1p, 0.5-0.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{105.5, 1.5-1.5p, 0.5-0.5p}	{919.9, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{229.975, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	229.975
5	{45.5, 1.5p-1.5p, 1.5p-1.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{151, 1.5-1.5p, 1.5-1.5p}	{965.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{193.08, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	193.08
6	{60.5, 1.5p-1.5p, 1.5p-1.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{211.5, 1.5-1.5p, 1.5-1.5p}	{1025.9, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{170.98, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	170.98
7	{91.5, 2.5p-2.5p, 2.5p-2.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{303, 2.5-2.5p, 2.5-2.5p}	{1117.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{159.63, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	159.63
8	{124,15-15p, 15-15p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{427, 15-15p, 15-15p}	{1241.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{155.17, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	155.17← Minimum
9	{184, 15-15p, 10-10p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{611, 15-15p, 15-15p}	{1425.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{158.37, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	158.37
10	{229,10-10p, 7.5-7.5p}	{20.6, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{840, 15-15p, 15-15p}	{1654.4, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	{165.44, 0.2-0.2p, 0.2-0.2p}	165.44

Based on Table 3, it is observed that the average cost per hundred hours reaches its minimum at 800 hours. The corresponding total average cost is represented as Rs. <155 + 0.2p, 155.17, 155.4 - 0.2p> (with Rs. 10,000 considered as 1 unit). Hence, it is recommended that the truck owner replaces the vehicle with a new one at the end of 800 hours. By applying the proposed method, truck owners gain the flexibility to make replacement decisions within the fuzzy interval $p \in [0,1]$.

Table 4: Decision maker's choice, $p \in [0,1]$

Values of p	Total Average Cost (Rs.10,000 = 1 unit)
0.00	<154.97, 155.17, 155.37>
0.1	<154.99, 155.17, 155.35>
0.15	<155, 155.17, 155.34>
0.2	<155.01, 155.17, 155.33>
0.25	<155.02, 155.17, 155.32>
0.3	<155.03, 155.17, 155.31>
0.35	<155.04, 155.17, 155.3>
0.4	<155.05, 155.17, 155.29>
0.45	<155.06, 155.17, 155.28>
0.5	<155.07, 155.17, 155.27>
0.55	<155.08, 155.17, 155.26>
0.6	<156.09, 155.17, 155.25>

Values of p	Total Average Cost (Rs.10,000 = 1 unit)
0.65	<155.1, 155.17, 155.24>
0.7	<155.11, 155.17, 155.23>
0.75	<155.12, 155.17, 155.22>
0.8	<155.13, 155.17, 155.21>
0.85	<155.14, 155.17, 155.2>
0.9	<155.15, 155.17, 155.19>
0.95	<155.16, 155.17, 155.18>
1.00	<155.17, 155.17, 155.17>

Figure 4.1: Parametric Triangular Fuzzy Number Representing Uncertain Value with Peak at 155.17

5. CONCLUSION

To maximize profit and minimize expenses, as reflected in Table 4, many industrial firms and military organizations continuously face the challenge of determining the optimal replacement time for durable or outdated equipment. This paper presents a mathematical approach that directly incorporates the model in its imprecise (fuzzy) form, without converting it into a crisp version. The proposed method is straightforward and easy to apply for calculating the optimal replacement time. While Biswas and Pramanik [10, 11] and Krishnaveni G. and Ganesan K. [14] have addressed similar problems using fuzzy concepts, their solutions ultimately rely on crisp values. However, in real-life scenarios, crisp values are rarely appropriate for imprecise situations. Therefore, a numerical example is provided to demonstrate how the proposed method preserves the imprecise nature of the problem while delivering a practical solution. This approach can also be extended to a triangular intuitionistic fuzzy replacement model, considering both changing and non-changing monetary values over time.

References

- 1) Zadeh L A 1965 Fuzzy sets *Information and control* **8** 338-353
- 2) Bellman R 1955 Equipment replacement policy. *Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics* **3** 133–136

Machinery and Production Engineering

ISSN 0024 919X

- 3) Dreyfus S E 1960 A generalized equipment replacement study. *Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics* **8** 425–435
- 4) Mahdavi M and Mahdavi M 2009 Optimization of age replacement policy using reliability based heuristic model *Journal of Scientific & Industrial Research* **68** 668-673
- 5) Zhao X F, Chen M and Nakagawa, T 2010 Three kinds of replacement models combined with additive and independent damages *In Proceedings of the Ninth International Symposium on Operations Research and Its Applications (ISORA'10)* 31–38
- 6) Chang P T 2005 Fuzzy strategic replacement analysis *European Journal of Operational Research* **160** 532–559
- 7) Balaganesan M and Ganesan K 2020 Fuzzy approach to determine optimum Economic life of equipment with change in money value. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and computing* **1040** 647-655
- 8) Balaganesan M and Ganesan K 2018 An approach to solve replacement problems under intuitionistic fuzzy nature. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **1000** 1-9
- 9) Al-Najjar B and Alsyouf, I 2003 Selecting the most efficient maintenance approach using fuzzy multiple criteria decisions making. *International Journal of Production Economics* **84** 84–100
- 10) Biswas P and Pramanik S 2011 Application of fuzzy ranking method to determine the replacement time for fuzzy replacement problem. *International Journal of Computer Applications* **25** 41-47
- 11) Biswas P and Pramanik S 2011 Fuzzy approach to replacement problem with value of money changes with time. *International Journal of Computer Applications* **30** 28-33
- 12) El-Kholy A M and Abdelali M A M 2016 A Comparative Study for Fuzzy Ranking Methods in Determining Economic Life of Equipment. *International Journal of Construction Engineering and Management* **5** 42-54
- 13) Esogbue A O and Hearnese W E 1998 On replacement models via a fuzzy set theoretic framework. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics* **28** 549–560
- 14) Krishnaveni G and Ganesan K 2018 New approach for the solution of two-person zero sum fuzzy games. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* **119** 405-414
- 15) Ming Ma, Menahem Friedman, Abraham kandel, A new fuzzy arithmetic, Fuzzy sets and systems, 108,83-90, (1999)